

Solution of Second order linear differential equation using Mathematical software

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Abstract — In this paper, mathematical programming approach is used to solve second order linear differential equation, solution of second order DE are obtained by general solution as well Laplace Transform in the form of programming using MATLAB software.

Keywords— Second order differential Equation, Mathematical Programming (MATLAB).

Introduction

As we know differential equation has vital role in mathematical modelling. Differential equation is used in various fields like Economics, Electrical, Civil, computer, Mechanical engineering and sciences. We know theoretically it is solved by general solution method (complementary solution + Particular integral = Total solution) as well mathematical tool i.e. Integral Transform (Laplace Transform), following are the real life examples of linear (or nonlinear) differential equations.

1. Linear Models with Initial Value Problems – spring/ mass system with free undamped motion, free damped motion and driven motion, LRC – series electrical circuit etc.
2. Linear Models with Boundary Value Problems – deflection of a beam, rotating string, temperature in sphere etc.
3. Non-linear Models- nonlinear springs, nonlinear pendulum, rocket motion, ballistic pendulum etc.

Atsa'am, D. D. et. Al. [1] has developed object oriented software to solve second order linear ordinary differential equations with constant coefficients. Ra'ft Abdelrahim and Zurni Omar [2] has proposed a new hybrid block method of order five for solving second-order ordinary differential equations directly, this method is developed using interpolation and collocation techniques.

Araceli Queiruga Dios et. al. [3] have proposed the students a term project that summarizes some of the knowledge and competences acquired during the lessons, also described study of the software and specific applications. E.S. Cheb-Terrab et. al. [4] has presented an update of the ODE tools Maple package, for the analytical solving of 1st and 2nd order ODEs using Lie group symmetry methods.

In this paper solution of second order linear differential equation model has been studied and solve using programming approach in MATLAB/ maple software.

Mathematical form of Second order linear Differential equation

general form of a second order linear differential equation as

$$ay'' + by' + cy = f(t)$$

where $a \neq 0, b$ and c are constants, with initial value condition $y(0) = y_0, y'(0) = y_1$.

To solve this IVP, general solution is obtained (i.e. complementary function as well particular integral) as well with the help of Laplace transform solution can be found.

Application

To solve second order Differential Equations, we can use general solution method i.e. by finding C.F and P.I. as well Laplace Transforms, to solve following second order D.E. problem MATLAB software R2013a is used.

Ex. Solve differential equation $\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + 7\frac{dx}{dt} + 10x = 20$, with $x(0) = 5, \frac{dx}{dt}(0) = 3$

To solve this problem in MATLAB following terms are used.

- syms – this command is used for to create symbolic variables and functions.
- subs – this command is used for symbolic substitution.

- laplace – this is inbuilt function used to solve Laplace transform
- ilaplace – this is inbuilt function used to solve inverse Laplace transform
- dsolve – this command is used for to solve ordinary differential equation

MATLAB Programming with the help of Laplace Transform

```
>> syms x t s X F
>>
F=laplace('diff(x(t),t,t)+7*diff(x(t),t)+10*x(t)
)=20',s)
```

F =

$$7*s*\text{laplace}(x(t), t, s) - D(x)(0) - 7*x(0) - s*x(0) + s^2*\text{laplace}(x(t), t, s) + 10*\text{laplace}(x(t), t, s) == 20/s$$

```
>> F=subs(F,{'laplace(x(t),t,s)'},{X})
```

F =

$$10*X - 7*x(0) - D(x)(0) + 7*X*s - s*x(0) + X*s^2 == 20/s$$

```
>> F=subs(F,{'x(0)','D(x)(0)'},{5,3})
```

F =

$$10*X - 5*s + 7*X*s + X*s^2 - 38 == 20/s$$

```
>> X=solve(F,'X')
```

X =

$$(5*s + 20/s + 38)/(s^2 + 7*s + 10)$$

```
>> x=ilaplace(X)
```

```
x =
```

```
6*exp(-2*t) - 3*exp(-5*t) + 2
```

MATLAB Program with dsolve command

```
>>
```

```
x=dsolve('D2x+7*Dx+10*x=20','x(0)=5','Dx  
(0)=3')
```

```
x =
```

```
6*exp(-2*t) - 3*exp(-5*t) + 2
```

```
>>
```

Conclusion

To solve second order differential equation MATLAB programming approach is used by using Laplace Transform method as well general method, with the help programming various critical problem can be solved.

References

- [1] Atsa'am, D. D. and Odeh, A. Pius, Design and Implementation of Object-Oriented Computer Software to Solve Second Order Ordinary Differential Equations with Constant Coefficients, International journal of scientific research in information

systems and engineering (IJSRISE), Vol. 1, No.1, 2015, pp. 17 – 28.

- [2] Ra'ft Abdelrahim and Zurni Omar, Direct Solution of Second-Order Ordinary Differential Equation Using a Single-Step Hybrid Block Method of Order Five, Math. Comput. Appl. 2016, 21, 12, pp. 1-7.

- [3] Araceli Queiruga Dios et. al., How Engineers deal with Mathematics solving Differential Equation, Procedia Computer Science Volume 51, 2015, pp. 1977–1985.

- [4] E.S. Cheb-Terrab et. al. , Computer Algebra Solving of Second Order ODEs Using Symmetry Methods, Symbolic Computation Group, Departamento de Física Teórica, IF-UERJ., <http://dft.if.uerj.br/preprint/e7-1.tex>, pp. 1 – 22.